

INTERFACE DESIGN OF CORD-RUBBER COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Cord-reinforced rubber composites are widely used in tires, hoses, belts and various attenuation constructions. The interfacial properties play a leading role in the performance and duration of the cord-rubber products. Therefore, optimal design of the interfacial properties is of great importance for improving and enhancing the product qualities. More attention has been paid to two ways, i.e., the addition of bonding agents to the rubber compounds and the adhesive treatment of the cords, to improve the interface strength[1]. However, there has been a little work concerning the mechanical design of the interface. Carman et al. [2] proposed an optimal method for the interfacial modulus by minimizing the maximum principal stress and the strain energy density in the composite materials. A zero-thickness interface and perfect bonding are usually assumed in the phenomenological approaches for the composite materials. In recent years, considerable work has been focused on the discussion of the imperfect interface[3,4]. Based upon the imperfect interface and the neutral inclusions that do not disturb the prescribed uniform stress field in the surrounding elastic body, Ru [3] presented the interface design of a single neutral elastic inclusion in many typical cases. In practice, the neutral inclusion does not exist if a perfectly bonded interface between inclusion and elastic body is assumed. Bertoldi et al.[4] concluded that a circular inclusion coated by a continuous structural interface was neutral for a far broader material parameter range than for the linear interface. In this work the interfacial parameters of the cord-rubber composites are studied by means of the concept of neutral inclusion.

2 Interface Design for Cord-Rubber in Anti-plane Shear

2.1 A General Neutrality Condition

According to the concept of the neutral inclusion, the embedded inclusion does not affect the original stress field. When the given stresses are applied to the inclusion, the displacement field can be calculated in the region of the inclusion. Based upon the transmission conditions along the interface, one may get the neutrality condition. Ru [3] has studied a general neutrality condition in this way for the neutral elastic inclusion.

Consider a single cord with shear modulus μ_2 embedded in the rubber with shear modulus μ_1 in anti-plane shear, where the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the rubber and cord, respectively. For the sake of simplicity, the rubber and cord are assumed to be the linear isotropic material. In terms of the Ru's analysis[3], the anti-plane displacement $w(x, y)$ satisfies the harmonic equilibrium equation in rubber matrix (D_1) and reinforcing phase(D_2), i.e.,

$$\nabla^2 w_i = 0, \text{ in } D_i (i=1,2) \quad (1)$$

The imperfect interface conditions along the interface (Γ) are given by

$$h(x, y)(w_1 - w_2) = \mu_1 \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial N} = \mu_2 \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial N} \quad (2)$$

where N is the direction of the outward normal to Γ and $h(x, y)$ the interfacial parameter proportional to the density of the adhesive layer. If there existed a neutrality condition for the cord-rubber composites, $h(x, y)$ must be non-negative everywhere.

Integration of Equ.(2) on the interface yields

$$w_2(x, y) = \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2} w_1(x, y) + w_0 \quad (3)$$

in which w_0 is an arbitrary value corresponding to a rigid body displacement. For convenience, w_0 is neglected in the following analysis for it does not contribute to the deformation. And then, the neutrality condition is rewritten as,

$$h(x, y) \left(1 - \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2}\right) w_1 = \mu_1 \left[\frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} \cos N(x, y) + \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} \sin N(x, y) \right] \quad (4)$$

This equation denotes the relation between the interface parameter $h(x, y)$ and the shape of cord.

2.2 Determination of Interfacial Parameters

The Nylon66 cord with twisting factor of 1400detex/2 is commonly used in a tire. A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) photograph in Fig.1 shows a non-circular cross-sectional construction for a single nylon66 cord embedded in the rubber matrix. Thus the cross-section of the cord is depicted by

$$\begin{cases} (x-a)^2 + y^2 = R^2, 0 \leq x \leq R+a \\ (x+a)^2 + y^2 = R^2, -(R+a) \leq x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

and plotted in Fig.2 where R is the radius of one strand.

In the case of the displacement field $w_1(x, y) = B_1 y$ which satisfies the harmonic equilibrium equation, the interfacial parameter $h(x, y)$ is given by

$$h(x, y) = \frac{\mu_1}{1 - \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2}} \frac{1}{R} \quad (6)$$

Since the stiffness of cord is much higher than that of rubber, or namely $\frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2} \approx 0$, the interfacial parameter is reduced to

$$h(x, y) = \frac{\mu_1}{R} \quad (7)$$

Clearly, the interfacial parameter is identical along the interface boundary and independent of the prescribed uniform stress field. Fig.4 shows the dimensionless parameter $H(x, y) = h(x, y)R / \mu_1$ as

indicated by the height of green shadow with a symbol of plus.

In the other case of the displacement field $w_1(x, y) = B_3 xy$ which also satisfies the harmonic equilibrium equation, the interfacial parameter is derived, i.e.,

$$h(x, y) = \begin{cases} \frac{2x-a}{Rx} \mu_1, 0 \leq x \leq R+a \\ \frac{2x+a}{Rx} \mu_1, -(R+a) \leq x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In the range of $-\frac{a}{2} < x < \frac{a}{2}$, the interface parameter

$h(x, y) < 0$, so $h(x, y)$ is out of the non-negative restriction. If the interfacial boundary at $-a < x < a$ is replaced by two lines parallel to the principle axis as shown in Fig.3, the interfacial parameter becomes

$$h(x, y) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu_1}{R}, |x| < a \\ \frac{2|x|-a}{R|x|} \mu_1, a \leq |x| \leq R+a \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Furthermore, a dimensionless parameter $H(x, y)$ is introduced to illustrate the interfacial parameter distribution along the interface Γ as follows,

$$H(x, y) = \frac{h(x, y)R}{\mu_1} = \begin{cases} 1, |x| < a \\ 2 - \frac{a}{|x|}, a \leq |x| \leq R+a \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

As illustrated in Fig.5, $H(x, y)$ is positive on the entire boundary. In addition, it is found that the interfacial parameter is also independent of the prescribed uniform stress field and the cord stiffness.

3 Interface Design for Cord-Rubber in Plane Deformations

3.1 Governing Equation

In the analysis of Ru[3], the imperfect interface condition along the interface Γ was described in the normal and tangential directions by

$$\llbracket \sigma_{nn} \rrbracket = 0, \llbracket \sigma_{nt} \rrbracket = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_{nn} = p(x, y) \llbracket u_n \rrbracket, \sigma_{nt} = q(x, y) \llbracket u_t \rrbracket \quad (12)$$

where $\llbracket * \rrbracket = (*)_1 - (*)_2$ denotes the jump across Γ , $p(x, y)$ and $q(x, y)$ are non-negative normal and tangential interface parameters, respectively. The stresses of σ_{nn} and σ_{nt} as well as the displacements of u_n and u_t are in the normal and tangential directions, respectively.

Consider the following uniform stress field on the rubber matrix, i.e.,

$$\sigma_x^{(1)} = A, \sigma_y^{(1)} = B, \tau_{xy}^{(1)} = C \quad (13)$$

in which A, B and C are the constants. The displacement field can be easily obtained in the framework of theory of elasticity,

$$\begin{cases} u_1 = \frac{A - \nu_1 B}{E_1} x + M_1 y + D_1 \\ v_1 = \frac{B - \nu_1 A}{E_1} y + \left(\frac{C}{\mu_1} - M_1 \right) x + F_1 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where ν is Poisson's ratio, and M, D and F are related to the rigid body motion.

For the neutral inclusion, the inclusion has the same stress field with the matrix,

$$\sigma_x^{(2)} = A, \sigma_y^{(2)} = B, \tau_{xy}^{(2)} = C \quad (15)$$

The superscripts (1) and (2) refer to the rubber and cord, respectively. Thus, the displacement field in the cord has the form,

$$\begin{cases} u_2 = \frac{A - \nu_2 B}{E_2} x + M_2 y + D_2 \\ v_2 = \frac{B - \nu_2 A}{E_2} y + \left(\frac{C}{\mu_2} - M_2 \right) x + F_2 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Substitution of Eqs.(14) and (16) into Equ.(12) leads to,

$$\begin{cases} p(x, y) [l(u_1 - u_2) + m(\nu_1 - \nu_2)] \\ \quad = l^2 A + m^2 B + 2lmC \\ q(x, y) [l(\nu_1 - \nu_2) - m(u_1 - u_2)] \\ \quad = lm(B - A) + (l^2 - m^2)C \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

In the manipulation, the rigid body motion is not taken into account, i.e., M, D and F are zero.

By application of Equ.(17), the interface property and the cord shape under an assumption of the neutral inclusion will be discussed in the next sections.

3.2 Equal-biaxial Tension

For a cord with a given shape as shown in Fig.2 under the equal-biaxial tension,

$$\sigma_x^{(2)} = \sigma_y^{(2)} = A = B, \tau_{xy}^{(2)} = C = 0 \quad (18)$$

And the interface parameters are derived from Equ.(17),

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{p(x, y)} = \left(\frac{1 - \nu_1}{E_1} - \frac{1 - \nu_2}{E_2} \right) \left(R - \frac{a^2}{R} + \frac{a}{R} |x| \right) \\ q(x, y) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

In view of the approximate incompressibility of the rubber and the significant difference in stiffness between the cord and the rubber, the interfacial parameters are reduced to,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{p(x, y)} = \frac{1}{2E_1} \left(R - \frac{a^2}{R} + \frac{a}{R} |x| \right) \\ q(x, y) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

After non-dimensionalization as done in section2.2, one may get

$$\begin{cases} P(x, y) = \frac{2E_1}{Rp(x, y)} = 1 - \frac{a^2}{R^2} + \frac{a}{R^2} |x| \\ Q(x, y) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Fig.6 shows the dimensionless normal parameter $P(x, y)$ as indicated by the height of green shadow along interface boundary Γ . Obviously, the interface parameters are non-negative on the entire interface. It should be noted that the interface property is also independent of the cord stiffness.

3.3 Uniaxial Tension

In the state of the uniaxial tension parallel to the x-axis,

$$\sigma_x^{(2)} = A, \sigma_y^{(2)} = 0, \tau_{xy}^{(2)} = 0 \quad (22)$$

The interface parameters are also derived from Equ.(17) and given by

$$\begin{cases} \frac{p(x,y)R}{E_1} [(x^2 - ax) - \frac{y^2}{2}] = (x-a)^2 \\ \frac{q(x,y)R}{E_1} \left(\frac{3x-a}{2} \right) = (x-a) \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Furthermore, the dimensionless quantities of $P(x, y)$ and $Q(x, y)$ are expressed by,

$$\begin{cases} P(x, y) = \frac{2(x-a)^2}{2(x^2 - ax) - y^2} \\ Q(x, y) = \frac{2(x-a)}{3x-a} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

As indicated in Fig.7, the red region with a symbol of minus shows the negative interfacial parameters, which is physically unavailable. Hence, the neutral cord does not exist under the uniaxial tension, no matter what the interface parameter is.

To obtain a neutral cord under the uniaxial tension, the interface boundary, along which the interfacial parameters are negative, is replaced by two lines parallel to the stress direction. As shown in Fig.8, the normal and tangential interface parameters are non-negative in the replaced region.

Consequently, for the designed cross-section of the cord, there exists a neutral cord in the anti-plane shear and plane deformations. In fact, this designed interface contour may be achieved by processing as shown in Fig.9.

4 Conclusions

Based upon the imperfect interface and the concept of a neutral inclusion, a neutrality condition for cord-rubber composites is obtained, and then the interfacial parameter is discussed in the anti-plane shear and plane deformations. It is found that the interface design for two-strand cord is available under an assumption of the neutral inclusion. In addition, the interfacial parameter is independent of the cord stiffness.

Fig.1. A cross-sectional construction for a single Nylon66 cord in rubber matrix.

Fig.2. A cross-section of a cord

Fig.3. Designed cross-sectional construction.

Fig.4. The dimensionless interfacial parameter under anti-plane shear, $w_1(x, y) = B_1 y$.

Fig.5. The dimensionless interfacial parameter under anti-plane shear, $w_1(x, y) = B_3xy$.

Fig.8. The dimensionless interfacial parameters under uniaxial tension.

Fig.6. The dimensionless normal interfacial parameter under equal-biaxial tension.

Fig.9. A SEM photograph of a single Nylon66 cord in rubber matrix

Fig.7. The dimensionless interfacial parameters under uniaxial tension.

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